

11-16 AUGUST 2019

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Nanosheet Array-like {001}TiO₂/g-C₃N₄ Heterostructured Hybrids for Highly Efficient Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution Under UV-vis Light Irradiation

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Photocatalysis

H₂ : ecofriendly high efficiency regeneration

Industrial route

Increasing consumption of energy

Semiconductor + solar energy

Heterogeneous photocatalysis reaction

Photocatalytic H₂ production

Photocatalytic degradation

Chen, et al. *Chem. Rev.*, 2010

Ma, et al. *Chem. Rev.*, 2014

Kapilashrami, et al. *Chem. Rev.*, 2014

Key: Design of novel photocatalysts

Anatase TiO₂

Optimal structure

Hierarchical structured
Nanorod, nanosphere,
nanowire

Good chemistry stability, low
lost, high activity

Enhanced light trapping,
Molecule diffusion/transportation

Increasing active sites,
accelerating surface reaction

Quantum size effect
tuning band gap

Eg (3.2 eV), low quantum efficiency, less exposed active (001) facets

Surface modification

Crystal
plane
tuning

Catalysts
asistant

Dye
sensitized

Doping

Non
metal

metal

Defect
tuning

Complexing

Z -mech
anism

I - II type
heterojun
cture

p-n
junction

Present TiO₂/g-C₃N₄ composites

Easy syn, stable, nontoxic, wide E_g

Match band structure, II-heterojunction

Chen, et al. *Appl. Catal. B: Environ*, 2016

Not enough uniform of the composite, Poor photodegradation activity

Solvent evaporation process

TiO₂ - g-C₃N₄ un-intimate connection, unfavorable for the separation of e⁻ -h⁺ pairs

Gu, et al. *J. Hazard Mater.*, 2014

Song, et al. *Appl. Catal. B: Environ.* 2016

Unfavorable exposure of active {001} facets

Ma, et al. *Int. J. Hydrogen. Energy.* 2016

Scientific questions

Uniform nanosheets array-like morphology of TiO_2 -g- C_3N_4 heterostructures are desired for improving the harvest of light and exposure of active facets. The high-risk HF-capping agent should be avoided from the aim of “green chemistry”.

It is highly desired to prepare a well-dispersed heterostructured $\{001\}\text{TiO}_2$ /g- C_3N_4 hybrids with strong light harvest and more exposed active sites via a green strategy for greatly enhanced photoreactivity.

Our Strategy

An in situ F-free solvothermal method using diethylenetriamine as capping and morphology controlled agent developed for fabricating a series of gram-level uniform nanosheet array-like heterostructured $\{001\}\text{TiO}_2$ /g- C_3N_4 hybrids.

The influence of incorporated narrow band gap g- C_3N_4 on the structure and photo-reactivity of hybrids have been carefully investigated. The close interfacial linkages, two-phase synergistic effect and possible photocatalytic mechanism were discussed upon the uniform nanosheet array-like morphology of the hybrids.

Synthesis strategy---In situ assemble

TC-x (x = 50, 100, 150, 175, 200 mg of g-C₃N₄)

Photocatalytic H₂ Evolution

UV-vis Light: 350-780 nm
 Sacrifice agent: CH₃OH-H₂O (20 vol%)
 Cocatalyst: 182 μL H₂PtCl₆·6H₂O
 Temperature: ~ 288±0.2 K

Results and Discussion --- structure, composition and morphology

Catalysts	D_{004} /nm	D_{200} /nm	percent of {001}/%
{001}TiO ₂	13.3	13.7	18.26
TC-50	12.9	12.9	17.46
TC -100	12.7	12.9	17.77
TC-150	10.8	12.0	17.04
TC-175	8.95	9.72	19.87
TC-200	9.78	10.3	18.94

$$\text{area of (001) face: } S_{001} = \left(D_{200} - \frac{D_{004}}{\tan \alpha} \right)^2$$

$$\text{area of (101) face: } S_{101} = \frac{1}{2} \left(2D_{200} - \frac{D_{004}}{\tan \alpha} \right) \times \frac{D_{004}}{2 \sin \alpha}$$

$$\text{percent of \{001\} = } \frac{2S_{001}}{2S_{001} + 8S_{101}} \times 100\%$$

**TiO₂ nanosheet - g-C₃N₄ surface complexation
no crystal lattice doping**

Intimate interface linkage

Strong interaction

Large SA, uniform mesopores, large volume of pores, favoring exposure of active sites

Strong interaction between TiO₂ and g-C₃N₄, forming close interface contact

Interface heterojunction & surface heterojunction

Construction of heterojunction may greatly improve separation between photogenerated electrons and holes

Performance of photocatalytic hydrogen production

26.20 mmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹

10 th, 95%

341.7 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹

Excellent H₂ production stability

Stability of TC-175 for photocatalytic hydrogen production

Well-kept nanosheet array-like morphology and heterostructure

Correlation between structure and photocatalytic property

Lowered E_g as a result of strong synergy

TC-175: the lowest $e^- - h^+$ recombination

Nanosheet array-like heterojunction efficiently improve the separation of photo-created $e^- - h^+$, accelerating surface transfer of the photo-created charge carriers

Prolonger lifetime of photo-created electron-holes pairs.

TC-175: smaller transfer resistance of surface charges and higher charge density than TiO₂ and g-C₃N₄

Plausible mechanism

Summary

Ultrathin nanosheet array-like heterostructured hybrids $\{001\}\text{TiO}_2/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ via an in situ F-free solvothermal route shows markedly enhanced photocatalytic H_2 evolution rate of $26.20 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ attributed to the high separation efficiency of photogenerated charge carriers upon $\text{TiO}_2 - \text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ interface heterojunctions and surface heterojunctions between $\{001\}$ and $\{101\}$ facets of TiO_2 and strong $\text{TiO}_2 - \text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ synergy.

The present work provides a novel method for the large-scale production of $\{001\}\text{TiO}_2$ -based heterojunction photocatalysts, which can be widely applied in solar energy conversion areas.

Acknowledgement

- Zhiyong Qiao, Jin Li, Ningan Wu, Zhuojun Wei

- State Key Laboratory of Chemical Resource Engineering

- College of Chemistry, BUCT

- National Natural Science Foundation of China